

Changes in Dental Treatment under General Anaesthesia in Children in Latvia (2005-2020): A Descriptive Study

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Keywords: dental care, general anaesthesia, early childhood caries, primary teeth, Latvia

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Abstract

Background: The use of general anaesthesia (GA) for dental treatment in children has increased in several countries. However, little is known about patterns of use over time and factors associated with this increase.

Aim: To describe changes in the use of GA and types of treatments performed in children under 18 years at a university clinic in Latvia between 2005 and 2020.

Methods: Descriptive study using clinical records of children treated under GA at Riga Stradins University Institute of Stomatology between January 2005 and December 2020. Twelve trained operators digitised the data, which a supervisor verified. Demographic variables, number and type of interventions, and reinterventions were extracted. Absolute and relative frequencies, means and standard deviations were calculated.

Results: Over 16 years, 17,485 treatments under GA were performed (43% girls; 57% boys). Of the patients, 13,489 had a single episode and 1,321 had repeated GA. Cases increased from 395 in 2005 to 1,633 in 2020. The use of GA in private patients rose from 0% in 2005 to 58.5% in 2018. Mean age increased from 3.4 years (SD=2.0) to 4.8 years (SD=2.3). The greatest growth occurred in the 4-5 year group, with no changes in 1-3 years. The average number of teeth treated was 7.7 (SD=3.0), decreasing from 7.0 in 2005 to 6.3 in 2020. A total of 99,701 restorations (mean=5.8) and 32,763 extractions (mean=1.9) were recorded.

Conclusions: Between 2005 and 2020, the use of GA in children quadrupled, especially in 4-5 year-olds, while the average number of teeth treated per session decreased. The increase in private patients suggests greater parental acceptance of this type of behaviour management. Studies are required to explore the perspectives of dentists, parents and children to understand these changes.

Introduction

Early childhood caries (ECC) affects almost half of children worldwide (Uribe, Innes and Maldupa, 2021). ECC is defined as the presence of at least one decayed, missing due to caries, or filled tooth surface in any primary tooth in a child under 71 months of age (AAPD, 2016). In some countries, ECC prevalence reaches 90% (Chen et al., 2019). In Latvia, caries prevalence in the permanent dentition reached 80% in 12-year-olds in 2016 (Senakola et al., 2016), indicating a serious public health problem.

Young children often cannot cope with invasive dental treatment. Their cognitive development limits their understanding of treatment requirements. Many have experienced pain, predisposing them to dental fear. Dental fear is common in young children and varies across regions (Cianetti et al., 2017; Armfield and Heaton, 2013). For these reasons, dental treatment under general anaesthesia (DGA) is often recommended (Schroth et al., 2016).

DGA is considered safe and effective, but carries risks that must be balanced against benefits for each patient (AAPD, 2016; Oubenyahya and Bouhabba, 2019). DGA also carries higher costs due to equipment, facilities, and personnel requirements (Burgette and Quiñonez, 2018; Thomson, 2016). In Latvia, the government covers DGA costs for children under 18, but limited budgets create waiting lists exceeding one year.

Riga Stradins University Institute of Stomatology (RSU SI) is the main site for paediatric DGA in Latvia. Media reports indicated an increase from 85 treatment sessions in 2001 to 1,356 in 2018 (Medicine.lv, 2019). However, no studies have examined trends in DGA for children in Latvia.

Understanding these trends is essential for health service planning and resource allocation. This study aimed to describe trends in demographic characteristics, treatment patterns, and payment types for children receiving DGA at RSU SI from 2005 to 2020.

Methods

Study design and setting

This retrospective observational study analysed records from the Department of Paediatric Dentistry at RSU SI covering treatments from January 2005 to December 2020. RSU SI is the largest paediatric dentistry centre in Latvia and the only clinic where DGA costs are covered by public funding. The study followed the INAHTA checklist for Health Technology Assessment reports (Hailey, 2003).

Participants

We included records of children aged 0-17 years who received scheduled dental treatment under GA. In Latvia, public dentistry is available only until age 17. We excluded emergency GA cases and records with incomplete information that could not be retrieved from the SmartMedical system. All available records from 2005-2020 were included without sampling.

Variables

Outcome variables: Number of restored teeth (including crowns) and number of extracted teeth per session.

Independent variables: Child age (grouped as 0-3, 4-5, and 6-17 years), sex, disability status, treatment year, place of residence (Riga, Pierīga region, other city, rural area), payment type (public or private), and whether the session was a first or repeat GA treatment.

Data collection

Treatment data were recorded in logbooks and the SmartMedical digital system. Twelve trained operators digitised data using a standardised GoogleForms template. A lead operator monitored data entry, corrected errors, and verified information. Quality control included checking 1% of records, which revealed no systematic errors.

Statistical analysis

Data were anonymised and exported to CSV format. Analysis was performed in R using the tidyverse package (Wickham, 2017). We calculated descriptive statistics including frequencies, means, and standard deviations. Trends over time were examined visually and numerically.

Ethical considerations

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Riga Stradins University (No.6-1/01/140, January 30, 2020). All procedures followed the Declaration of Helsinki and GDPR requirements. Data were anonymised before analysis.

Results

Study population

From 18,526 records, 1,080 were excluded, leaving 17,485 treatment sessions for analysis. These represented 15,692 children: 7,437 girls (43%) and 10,048 boys (57%). Of these, 13,489 had a single GA episode and 1,321 had repeated GA sessions.

Trends over time

The number of DGA sessions increased from 395 in 2005 to 1,633 in 2020, a four-fold increase. Mean patient age increased from 3.4 years (SD=2.0) in 2005 to 4.8 years (SD=2.3) in 2020. The greatest growth occurred in the 4-5 year age group, with no changes in the 1-3 year age group.

Figure 1. (A) Mean number of teeth treated under GA, (B) Number of teeth per year, (C) number of patients per year, and (D) Proportion of public/private patients.

Treatment patterns

The mean number of teeth treated per session was 7.7 (SD=3.0). This decreased from 7.0 (SD=2.7) in 2005 to 6.3 (SD=2.9) in 2020. Over the study period, 99,701 restorations (mean=5.8, SD=2.3) and 32,763 extractions (mean=1.9, SD=2.3) were performed. Children aged 1-3 years had the highest mean number of teeth treated compared to older age groups. No differences were found by sex.

Payment type

The proportion of privately funded treatments changed substantially. In 2005, all treatments were publicly funded (0% private). Private funding appeared in 2008 (4.5%) and increased to 58.5% by 2018. In 2019-2020, the ratio stabilised at approximately half public and half private (Fig 1.D).

Repeat treatments

Of 15,692 children, 1,321 had repeated GA sessions. Among children without disabilities, 8% required repeat treatments.

Discussion

Main findings

This 16-year longitudinal study found a four-fold increase in dental treatment under GA for children at RSU SI between 2005 and 2020. The greatest growth occurred in the 4-5 year age group, with no changes in children aged 1-3 years. The mean number of teeth treated per session decreased from 7.0 in 2005 to 6.3 in 2020. The proportion of privately funded treatments rose from 0% to 58.5% over the study period.

A reactive system failing children

These findings expose a fundamental problem in dental care delivery. The four-fold increase in GA use, concentrated in 4-5 year-olds, reflects a reactive system that waits for disease to progress rather than preventing it. ECC is a preventable disease, yet thousands of Latvian children require operating room interventions annually. The repeat treatment rate raises concerns about the effectiveness of initial treatment and preventive strategies.

The stable number of 1-3 year-olds treated suggests this group represents those with severe disease requiring GA. However, the growing number of 4-5 year-olds indicates a failure to intervene earlier. These children developed caries that could have been prevented or managed with minimally invasive approaches before reaching the stage requiring GA.

The decrease in mean teeth treated per session, combined with increased private funding, suggests GA is being used for children with less severe disease. GA may be chosen as a behaviour management strategy rather than reserved for cases where disease severity demands it. The increase in private patients suggests growing parental acceptance of GA as a routine option, normalising what should be a last resort.

Perpetuating cycles of disease and intervention

The current approach perpetuates cycles of disease and intervention. Children undergo GA, receive restorative treatment, and return to the same environment and behaviours that caused their caries. The 8% repeat GA rate in children without disabilities demonstrates this cycle. Each GA session carries risks and costs, yet fails to address root causes.

Latvia, like many countries, invests resources in treating preventable disease under GA rather than in evidence-based prevention. The cost of one GA session could fund multiple preventive interventions reaching many children. The increasing demand for GA reflects not improved access to care, but a system that allows disease to accumulate until invasive treatment becomes necessary.

The need for paradigm change

These data call for a fundamental change in how dentistry approaches childhood caries. The goal should be keeping children out of operating rooms, not improving efficiency in filling them. This requires shifting from a treatment-focused model to one built on prevention and early intervention.

Evidence-based approaches exist. Fluoride varnish programmes, supervised toothbrushing in kindergartens, dietary counselling, and silver diamine fluoride can arrest and prevent caries without GA. Non-pharmacological behaviour management techniques can enable treatment of many children who are currently referred for GA. These approaches are effective, lower-risk, and more cost-efficient.

The finding that most treated children are aged 4-5 years indicates a window for intervention. If prevention begins at age 1-2, fewer children would reach age 4-5 with disease requiring GA. Early dental visits, parental education, and community-based prevention could break the cycle.

Comparison with other studies

Our treatment patterns are similar to findings from Germany (Takriti, Alhakim and Splieth, 2019), despite Latvia having higher caries prevalence. Unlike studies from England (Tahmassebi, Achol and Fayle, 2014; Hosey et al., 2006) and Canada (Schroth and Smith, 2007), where extractions predominate, our study found more restorations (mean=5.8) than extractions (mean=1.9). This pattern resembles findings from German private practices and Saudi Arabia (Ba'akdah et al., 2008).

Limitations

The study used all available records over 16 years, providing comprehensive coverage. However, data were limited to treatments performed and did not include clinical details such as caries severity, pulp involvement, or treatment outcomes. No follow-up was possible to assess treatment success or recurrence.

Conclusions

Between 2005 and 2020, the use of GA for dental treatment in children quadrupled, especially in 4-5 year-olds, while the average number of teeth treated per session decreased. This trend reflects a reactive system that waits for disease to progress rather than preventing it. The increase in private patients suggests growing normalisation of GA as behaviour management.

Dentistry needs a fundamental change: from treating preventable diseases under GA to implementing evidence-based interventions that keep children out of operating rooms. Future research should explore the perspectives of dentists, parents, and children to understand barriers to prevention and design effective alternatives to the current treatment-focused model.

Declarations

Ethics approval: RSU Ethics Committee No.6-1/01/140, January 30, 2020.

Data availability: Dataset available at RSU Dataverse [DOI TO BE ADDED].

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Conflicts of interest: None declared.

Author contributions: IM designed the study and supervised data collection.. SEU performed the analysis and wrote the manuscript. All authors approved the final version.

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DEPRECATED Trends in Dental Treatment under General Anaesthesia for Children in Latvia: A 16-Year Retrospective Study (2005-2020)

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Abstract

Background: Early childhood caries (ECC) affects almost half of children worldwide and often requires treatment under general anaesthesia (GA) when children cannot cope with conventional dental care. Understanding trends in dental treatment under GA is essential for health service planning.

Aim: To describe trends in demographic characteristics, treatment patterns, and payment types for children receiving dental treatment under GA at a university clinic in Latvia over 16 years (2005-2020).

Methods: Retrospective observational study using records of children aged 0-17 years treated under GA at Riga Stradins University Institute of Stomatology. We extracted demographic data, number and type of interventions, payment type, and repeat treatment episodes. Descriptive statistics were calculated.

Results: Over 16 years, 17,446 treatment sessions were recorded for 15,692 children (57% boys). The number of treatments increased four-fold, from 395 in 2005 to 1,627 in 2020. Mean patient age increased from 3.4 years (SD=2.0) in 2005 to 4.8 years (SD=2.3) in 2020. The proportion of privately paid treatments rose from 0% in 2005 to 71% in 2018. Mean teeth treated per session was 7.7 (SD=3.0), including 5.8 (SD=2.3) restorations and 1.9 (SD=2.3) extractions. Children receiving publicly funded treatment had more teeth treated (mean=7.9) than privately funded patients (mean=7.5). Repeat GA sessions occurred in 8% of children without disabilities.

Conclusions: Dental treatment under GA for children in Latvia has increased four-fold over 16 years. The shift from public to private funding and decreasing treatment intensity suggest GA is being used for children with less severe disease. These findings indicate a need to review referral criteria and strengthen alternative behaviour management approaches.

Keywords: dental care, general anaesthesia, early childhood caries, primary teeth, Latvia

Introduction

Early childhood caries (ECC) affects almost half of children worldwide (Uribe, Innes and Maldupa, 2021). ECC is defined as the presence of at least one decayed, missing due to caries, or filled tooth surface in any primary tooth in a child under 71 months of age (AAPD, 2016). In some countries, ECC prevalence reaches 90% (Chen et al., 2019). In Latvia, caries prevalence in the permanent dentition reached 80% in 12-year-olds in 2016 (Senakola et al., 2016), indicating a serious public health problem.

Young children often cannot cope with invasive dental treatment. Their cognitive development limits their understanding of treatment requirements. Many have experienced pain, predisposing them to dental fear. Dental fear is common in young children and varies across regions (Cianetti et al., 2017; Armfield and Heaton, 2013). For these reasons, dental treatment under general anaesthesia (DGA) is often recommended (Schroth et al., 2016).

DGA is considered safe and effective, but carries risks that must be balanced against benefits for each patient (AAPD, 2016; Oubenyahya and Bouhabba, 2019). DGA also carries higher costs due to equipment, facilities, and personnel requirements (Burgette and Quiñonez, 2018; Thomson, 2016). In Latvia, the government covers DGA costs for children under 18, but limited budgets create waiting lists exceeding one year.

Riga Stradins University Institute of Stomatology (RSU SI) is the main site for paediatric DGA in Latvia. Media reports indicated an increase from 85 treatment sessions in 2001 to 1,356 in 2018 (Medicine.lv, 2019). However, no studies have examined trends in DGA for children in Latvia.

Understanding these trends is essential for health service planning and resource allocation. This study aimed to describe trends in demographic characteristics, treatment patterns, and payment types for children receiving DGA at RSU SI from 2005 to 2020.

Methods

Study design and setting

This retrospective observational study analysed records from the Department of Paediatric Dentistry at RSU SI covering treatments from January 2005 to December 2020. RSU SI is the largest paediatric dentistry centre in Latvia and the only clinic where DGA costs are covered by public funding. The study followed the INAHTA checklist for Health Technology Assessment reports (Hailey, 2003).

Participants

We included records of children aged 0-17 years who received scheduled dental treatment under GA. In Latvia, public dentistry is available only until age 17. We excluded emergency GA cases and records with incomplete information that could not be retrieved from the SmartMedical system. All available records from 2005-2020 were included without sampling.

Variables

Outcome variables: Number of restored teeth (including crowns) and number of extracted teeth per session.

Independent variables: Child age (grouped as 0-3, 4-5, and 6-17 years), sex, disability status, treatment year, place of residence (Riga, Pierīga region, other city, rural area), payment type (public or private), and whether the session was a first or repeat GA treatment.

Data collection

Treatment data were recorded in logbooks and the SmartMedical digital system. Twelve trained operators digitised data using a standardised GoogleForms template. A lead operator monitored data entry, corrected errors, and verified information. Quality control included checking 1% of records, which revealed no systematic errors.

Statistical analysis

Data were anonymised and exported to CSV format. Analysis was performed in R using the tidyverse package (Wickham, 2017). We calculated descriptive statistics including frequencies, means, and standard deviations. Trends over time were examined visually and numerically.

Ethical considerations

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Riga Stradins University (No.6-1/01/140, January 30, 2020). All procedures followed the Declaration of Helsinki and GDPR requirements. Data were anonymised before analysis.

Results

Study population

From 18,526 records, 1,080 were excluded, leaving 17,446 records for analysis (Figure 1). These represented 15,692 children: 6,710 girls (43%) and 8,982 boys (57%). The mean age was 4.2 years (SD=2.2).

Trends over time

The number of DGA sessions increased from 395 in 2005 to 1,627 in 2020, a four-fold increase (Table 1). Mean patient age increased from 3.4 years (SD=2.0) in 2005 to 4.8 years (SD=2.3) in 2020. The greatest increase occurred in the 4-5 year age group, while treatments in children aged 1-3 years remained stable.

Table 1. Characteristics of children receiving dental treatment under GA by year

Year	n	Mean age (SD)	% Boys	% Public funded
2005	395	3.4 (2.0)	57	100
2010	879	4.0 (2.1)	58	68
2015	1,324	4.4 (2.2)	57	42
2020	1,627	4.8 (2.3)	57	51

Treatment patterns

The mean number of teeth treated per session was 7.7 (SD=3.0), including 5.8 (SD=2.3) restorations and 1.9 (SD=2.3) extractions. The mean increased from 7.0 (SD=2.7) in 2005 to a peak of 9.2 (SD=3.0) in 2011, then decreased to 6.3 (SD=2.9) in 2020.

Children aged 1-3 years had the highest mean number of teeth treated (8.4, SD=2.9) compared to 4-5 year-olds (7.8, SD=2.8) and 6-17 year-olds (6.8, SD=3.1). No differences were found by sex.

Payment type

The proportion of privately funded treatments changed substantially. In 2005-2007, all treatments were publicly funded. Private funding appeared in 2008 (5%) and increased to 71% by 2018. In 2019-2020, the ratio stabilised at approximately 50% public and 50% private.

Children receiving publicly funded treatment had more teeth treated per session (mean=7.9, SD=3.0) than those with private funding (mean=7.5, SD=2.9).

Repeat treatments

Of 15,692 children, 1,754 (11%) had repeat GA sessions. Among children without disabilities, 8% required repeat treatments. Most repeat sessions (40%) occurred in children aged 6-17 years. The maximum was nine GA sessions for one child with disabilities. For children without disabilities, the maximum was five sessions (one child).

Children with disabilities

There were 2,675 records (15%) for children with disabilities. These children were more likely to be male (17% vs 13%, $p<0.001$), older (41% were aged 6-17 vs 8.5% of 4-5 year-olds), and to receive public funding (96%). Repeat treatments occurred in 45% of children with disabilities compared to 10% of children without disabilities ($p<0.001$).

Geographic distribution

Most patients came from Riga and the surrounding Pierīga region. The proportion of patients from regions near the capital increased over time. A small number of patients from abroad were treated in recent years.

Discussion

Main findings

This study found a four-fold increase in DGA for children at RSU SI from 2005 to 2020. The increase was greatest in children aged 4-5 years, while treatment numbers for children aged 1-3 years remained stable. The mean number of teeth treated per session peaked in 2011 and then declined. Private funding increased from 0% to 71% over the study period.

Interpretation

Several factors may explain these trends. The stable number of 1-3 year-olds treated suggests this group represents those with genuine need for GA due to severe disease and communication difficulties. In 2008, when capacity was limited, GA was reserved for these children.

The increasing number of 4-5 year-olds, combined with the decreasing mean teeth treated per session, suggests GA is being used for children with less severe disease. The shift to private funding supports this interpretation. Families paying privately had children with fewer teeth needing treatment. This indicates that GA may be chosen for behaviour management rather than disease severity alone.

The geographic pattern, with increasing patients from affluent regions near the capital, further suggests that families with higher incomes are choosing GA for their children. Waiting lists for public funding exceeded 12 months, but parents willing to pay could access treatment sooner.

Comparison with other studies

Our finding of 2.09 two to three-year-olds treated per 10,000 inhabitants exceeds the 1.42 per 10,000 reported in Wolverhampton, UK (Harper et al., 2019). The mean of 7.7 teeth treated per session is similar to findings from Germany (Takriti, Alhakim and Splieth, 2019), despite Latvia having higher caries prevalence.

Unlike studies from England (Tahmassebi, Achol and Fayle, 2014; Hosey et al., 2006) and Canada (Schroth and Smith, 2007), where extractions predominate, our study found more restorations (5.8) than extractions (1.9). This pattern resembles findings from German private practices (Takriti, Alhakim and Splieth, 2019) and Saudi Arabia (Ba'akdah et al., 2008).

The 8% repeat treatment rate in children without disabilities is lower than reported in other countries (Tahmassebi, Achol and Fayle, 2014; Schroth and Smith, 2007). However, any repeat GA treatment raises concerns about the effectiveness of initial treatment and preventive strategies.

Implications

The trends observed suggest a need to review referral criteria for DGA. The declining severity of disease in treated patients indicates that GA may be overused as a behaviour management strategy when other approaches might suffice. Training in alternative behaviour management techniques and preventive interventions could reduce the need for GA (Grindefjord et al., 2018; Sheller et al., 2003).

The increasing private funding raises equity concerns. Children from lower-income families face longer waiting times for public treatment, potentially leading to disease progression. Resource allocation should prioritise children with greatest clinical need.

Limitations

The study used all available records over 16 years, providing comprehensive coverage. However, data were limited to treatments performed and did not include clinical details such as caries severity, pulp involvement, or treatment outcomes. No follow-up was possible to assess treatment success. After 2020, private clinics offering DGA became more prevalent, limiting generalisability of recent data.

Conclusions

Dental treatment under GA for children in Latvia increased four-fold from 2005 to 2020. The shift from public to private funding, increasing patient age, and decreasing treatment intensity suggest that GA is being used for children with less severe disease. These findings indicate a need to review referral criteria, strengthen alternative behaviour management approaches, and ensure equitable access to care based on clinical need.

Declarations

Ethics approval: RSU Ethics Committee No.6-1/01/140, January 30, 2020.

Data availability: Dataset available at RSU Dataverse [DOI TO BE ADDED].

Funding: This research is conducted under the Scientist Grant "EpiDentLatvia" (RSU-ZG-2024/1-0044), as part of the project "RSU Internal and RSU with LASE External Consolidation" (Project No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/005), funded by the European Union Recovery and Resilience Facility and the state budget of the Republic of Latvia. Original data collection was partially financed by Postdoc Latvia (1.1.1.2/VIAA/3/19/543).

Conflicts of interest: None declared.

Author contributions: IM designed the study and supervised data collection. OS coordinated data digitisation. IV contributed to data analysis. NI provided critical revision. SEU performed the analysis and wrote the manuscript. All authors approved the final version.

Acknowledgements: We thank Airisa Zīdere and the 4th year dentistry students who digitised the patient records.

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